

Influence of Recurrent & Capital Expenditure on Own Source of Revenue of Local Governments in Bagmati Province of Nepal

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Abstract

This paper analyses the trends in recurrent and capital expenditures among local governments (LGs) in the Bagmati Province of Nepal. Adopting a descriptive-analytical approach, the study utilizes panel data covering the fiscal years 2019/20 to 2023/24 across 119 LGs, totalling 595 observations. Data were sourced from the Financial Comptroller General Office (FCGO) and the National Statistics Office Government of Nepal. The results indicate a structural shift in budget allocation: while the five-year average share of the capital budget was 52.24%, it exhibited a declining trend, falling from 55% in 2019/20 to 49.1% in 2023/24. Conversely, the recurrent budget share rose from 44.46% to 50.72% over the same period. In terms of actual utilization, recurrent expenses accounted for 55.87% of total spending, compared to 43.94% for capital expenses, signaling nominal growth in recurrent spending against a marginal decline in capital expenditure. Although Own Source Revenue (OSR) increased from NPR 14.68 billion to NPR 17.29 billion, the financial independence rate deteriorated over the first three years, showing marginal recovery in the fifth year. Regression analysis reveals that recurrent and capital expenditures are strong predictors of OSR ($R^2=0.8412$), indicating a statistically significant positive relationship. The study concludes that while expenditures significantly influence revenue generation, trends vary notably across different geographical regions and types of local governments.

Keywords: *capital expenditure, recurrent expenses, own source of revenue, financial independence, budget spending rates, total revenue*